

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MOTIVATION FOR THE USE OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE AND ACTION TO RELIEVE TOOTH PAIN IN COMMUNITY IN MEUNASAH VILLAGE BLANG PIDIE JAYA

Ainun Mardiah ^{1*}, Reza ², Sukarsih ³ and Cut Aja Nuraskin ⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Department of Dental Health, Polytechnic, Ministry of Health, Aceh.

*Corresponding Author Email: ainunmardiah0166@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13842607](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842607)

Abstract

Traditional treatment for prophylaxis of dental and oral diseases is still often used and believed by the public can cure disease or eliminate the symptoms of disease and have properties for certain diseases based on the experience of use. The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship of the motivation of people in the use of traditional medicine to relieve toothache in communities Meunasah Blang Pidie Jaya. This research is analytic with cross sectional design. The population in this study is the whole village of Meunasah Blang and a sample of 91 people and taken based on systematic sampling technique. Data collected from interviews using questionnaires. The results of the study showed no association with measures of intrinsic motivation eliminate tooth pain ($P < 0.05$). Concluded that there is a relationship of intrinsic motivation to act relieve toothache and recommended to all people over the information multiply use traditional medicine in the right dose.

Keywords: Motivation, Traditional Medicine, Action Eliminate Pain Dental.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional medicine in Indonesia plays a very large role in public health services and has great potential for its development because our country is rich in medicinal plants. Traditional medicine is an ingredient or ingredient in the form of liquids, animals, minerals, salian sarian (galenik), or a mixture of these ingredients that have traditionally been used for treatment.

Traditional health services are treatment and care by referring to the experience of hereditary skills empirically that can be accounted for and applied in accordance with the norms that apply in society. Indonesian people still use a lot of traditional medicine for dental health to relieve tooth pain, the use of traditional medicine reaches 34.88%.² These developments have encouraged business growth in the field of traditional medicine, starting from the cultivation of medicinal plants, the drug industry and its distribution.

There is a strong tendency to use treatment with natural ingredients, not only in Indonesia, but also in various countries because this way of treatment applies the concept of 'back to nature' or return to nature which is believed to have fewer side effects than modern medicines. In public health services, it is quite large and in order to become an element in this system, traditional medicine needs to be further developed in order to meet the requirements of safety, efficacy, and quality. An urgent situation where finished drugs are not available or because they are not affordable by people's purchasing power.

Motivation is a person's encouragement to be able to do things more easily in using traditional medicine, the reason people are motivated to use traditional medicine because to cure diseases or eliminate the symptoms of diseases that are quite common, traditional medicine has efficacy for certain diseases based on the

experience of use. Data at the Meureudu Health Center from January to December 2018 where the number of patients with pulp and periapical tissue disease reached 106 cases of people suffering from gum and periodontal tissue disease.

The data shows that dental and oral diseases are still high in the community. The people in Meunasah Blang Village still use a lot of traditional medicine for treatment and many people use traditional medicine to relieve pain, namely castor sap to treat cavities, castor leaves to treat bleeding gums, betel leaves for toothache and swollen gums, lime for toothache and swollen gums, garlic to prevent pain in cavities, swelling and as an antibiotic, clove oil to relieve the pain of cavities.

This study aims to find out the relationship between community motivation in using traditional medicine to relieve toothache in the community in Meunasah Blang Village, Pidie Jaya.

METHODS

This study is analytical with a cross-sectional design, the population in this study is the entire community of Meunasah Blang village, Bandar Dua Pidie Jaya District which totals 983 people while the sample in the study is 91 people using systematic sampling techniques. The independent variable (influence) is intrinsic motivation, while the dependent variable (affected) is the action of relieving toothache.

The instrument used in this study is a questionnaire. Data analysis in this study uses a statistical test with a chi square test. Data analysis used Program for Social Science Statistics (SPSS), with hypothesis testing based on a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

The results of the research carried out on the community in Meunasah Blang Village, Pidie Jaya which was carried out from April to June 2019. Bivariate analysis aims to determine the relationship between the independent variable, namely intrinsic motivation, and the dependent variable, namely the action of relieving toothache. The results of the statistical analysis are presented below.

The Relationship Between Intrinsic Motivation and Toothache Relief Actions

The relationship between intrinsic motivation for the use of traditional medicine and the action of eliminating toothache in the community in the village Meunasah Blang Pidie Jaya can be seen in the following table

No	Intrinsic Motivation	Toothache relief				Total	%	Statistical Test Results
		Not good	%	Good	%			
1.	Low	14	15,4	11	12,1	25	100	P = 0.005 df = 1 $\alpha = 0,05$
2.	Tall	15	16,5	51	56,0	66	100	
Sum		29	31,9	62	68,1	91	100	

Based on the table above, it can be seen that there is a relationship between motivation for the use of traditional medicine and the action of relieving toothache in the community in Meunasah Blang Village, Bandar Dua District, Pidie Jaya with the results of the analysis using the Chi-Square Test showing that $p=0.005$ means that there is a statistically significant relationship ($p<0.05$).

The relationship of community motivation in using traditional medicine to relieve toothache in the community in Meunasah Blang, Bandar Dua Pidie Jaya District The results of the study with statistical test analysis with the chi square test, showed that there was a relationship between motivation for the use of traditional medicine and the action of relieving toothache in the community in Meunasah Blang Village

Bandar Dua Pidie Jaya District, statistically means $p=0.005$ ($p<0.05$). This is because people still prioritize pangalaman in terms of treating toothache for reasons that are easy to get, cheap and around the house so that people use a lot of traditional medicine for treatment, in addition to that many use traditional medicine to relieve pain such as castor sap to treat cavities, castor leaves to treat bleeding gums, betel leaves for toothache and swollen gums, lime for toothache and swollen gums, garlic to prevent pain in cavities, swelling and as an antibiotic, clove oil to relieve cavities.

Self-treatment is an effort to treat toothache using traditional medicine or traditional methods without expert guidance.⁵ Experience, is an event that a person has experienced in interacting with his environment.⁸ reviews

High intrinsic motivation with the action of relieving toothache because traditional medicine to relieve toothache is easier to get but there are other factors related to the act of using traditional medicine, namely influenced such as knowledge, experience, socio-economics and others.

Social motivation is an encouragement to act. A person gains knowledge through sensing a particular object. Knowledge is obtained as a result of stimuli captured by the five senses. Knowledge can be obtained naturally or planned, namely through the educational process. Knowledge is a very important realm for the formation of action.

CONCLUSION

After conducting a study on the relationship of community motivation in using traditional medicine to relieve toothache in the community in Meunasah Blang Village, Bandar Dua District, Pidie Jaya, it can be concluded that there is a relationship of community motivation in using traditional medicine to relieve pain $p=0.005$ statistically ($p<0.05$).

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusion, the following can be suggested, it is hoped that the public can add insight by increasing information and increasing motivation to use traditional medicine with the correct dosage and in accordance with the action of eliminating toothache.

It is hoped that there will be guidance and counseling by the health center to the community about the appropriate and correct use of traditional medicine.

References

- 1) Shirazuddin, Abbas.2014. PERBEDAAN SISTEM PENGOBATAN MEDIS dan NONMEDIS.<http://sirouzs.wordpress.com/2014/05/31/perbedaan-sistem-pengobatan-medis-dan-non-medis/di-kutip-28-desember-2014>.
- 2) Depkes RI. 2009. Profil Kesehatan Gigi Dan Mulut. Direktorat Kesehatan Gigi. Jakarta
- 3) Maryani, H. 2003. Tanaman obat untuk mengatasi penyakit pada usia lanjut. Hal 43-44,surabaya. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=ux2OKcYw1UcC&printsec=frontcover&dq=tanaman+obat+untuk+mengatasi+penyakit+pada+usia+lanjut>
- 4) Moeljantoe dan mulyono, 2003. Khasiat dan manfaat daun sirih. sagromedia pustaka.Jakarta. <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=vjdjnTBp9fsC&printsec=frontcover&dq=khasiat+dan+manfaat+daun+sirih>.
- 5) Sudibyo dan Andi, 2007. Jurnal penelitian penggunaan obat tradisional dalam upaya pengobatan sendiri di indonesia. Jakarta
- 6) Notoadmodjo. S, 2011. Kesehatan Masyarakat Ilmu Dan Seni. Rineka Cipta. Jakarta
- 7) Agoes, Azwar.2010. tanaman obat indonesia. Hal 38, salemba medika, jakarta
- 8) Notoatmodjo 2007. kesehatan masyarakat ilmu dan seni. rineka cipta.jakarta
- 9) Budiharto. 2009. pengantar ilmu perilaku kesehatan dan pendidikan kesehatan gigi. Hal 39.EGC.Jakarta